

Interconnection of Cartoon Watching with Blood in Urine

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ABSTRACT

If someone is interested in cartoon watching then there will be some chances to cause hematuria. The main motive of the study was to interconnect cartoon watching with blood in urine. Blood in urine causes hematuria. It causes serious diseases in human. It causes health problems. There were about 100 students involved in this research. All of them were the students of Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan. They were between the age of 19-22. They shared their point of views about the affection and detest of cartoon watching.

Keywords: Cartoons, Blood in urine, Fantasy, Fiction, Health problems.

1. Introduction

Blood in urine is a medical term which is called as hematuria. There are present different causes and diseases which can cause hematuria. It include infection, kidney disease, cancer and some others. Any blood in urine can be the sign of serious health problem. The blood may be visible but in some cases it is present in such a small quantity that it can not be seen by naked eye. Ignoring of hematuria can lead to serious disorders like kidney disease, cancer etc. [1] there are present two types of hematuria and these are gross hematuria and microscopic hematuria.

In some cases there is present excess of blood in urine that it turns into pink or red than it will be gross hematuria but in other cases if there is present small quantity of blood in urine that it can not be seen than it will be microscopic hematuria. The causes of hematuria are cancer, kidney disease, infection, stones, and enlarged prostate. There are present certain medications that can cause hematuria like penicillin, aspirin etc. There are present certain preventions from hematuria firstly drink plenty of water, practice good hygiene, urinate after sexual intercourse [2].

The cartoon watching has a connection with blood in urine. As the cartoon watching is a source of entertainment and joy. It is a source of entertainment not only for kids but also for adults. It releases all the tension of the whole day and also refresh mind and the science fiction cartoons also contain a huge knowledge. Thus, one of its aspect is that it is also a source of knowledge. The cartoons are also of different kinds like animated, science fictions, funny and fantasy. Not only kids but adults are also interested to watch cartoons to get rid of all of their tentions. Cartoon watching may also have some other issues like change in their behavior [3].

The main purpose of the current study was to affiliate cartoon watching with blood in urine. If someone is interested in cartoon watching then there will be some chances to cause hematuria

2. Material and Method

About 100 students were involved in this study and all of them were the students of Bahauddin Zakariya University Multan. They all were between the ages of 19-22.

Detection of urine in blood

A test named as urinalysis test is used to detect that whether there is blood in urine or not. It is used to measure a huge amount of disorders. It includes analysis of appearance, content and concentration of urine. Abnormal urinalysis may point to a disease. In this method the urine sample is evaluated in three ways visual exam, dipstick test and microscopic exam than the urine is tested for diseases.

Design

A questionnaire was prepared for the interconnection of blood in urine with cartoon watching.

Statistical

By using MS word analysis was performed.

3. Result and Discussion

Blood in urine	Likeness of cartoon watching	Dislikeness of cartoon watching
Total males are 20	75% males liked cartoon watching	25% males disliked cartoon watching
Total females are 80	66.5% females liked cartoon watching.	33.5% females disliked cartoon watching.

In this research there were total 100 students out of which 20 were males and 80 were females and all were the students of University and in males 75% showed likeness of cartoon watching and 25% showed dislikeness of cartoon watching. While 66.5% females showed likeness of cartoon watching and 33.5% showed dislikeness of cartoon watching. There may be some hormonal changes involved in this. This questionnaire based study is good and helpful in illustrating such type of research [4].

4. Conclusion

It was concluded from the following study that the topmost students liked cartoon watching while the minimum of them do not like the cartoon watching.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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